

Polish-Italian cooperation in assessing environmental threats using the European research platform SIOS

- Exploring and indicating national and EU funding instruments/opportunities and good practices of cooperation from EU PolarNet and bilateral project HarSval -

Location: Scientific Center of the Polish Academy of Sciences in Rome

Date: 10-11 December 2024

BACKGROUND/MOTIVATION

Since 2010, Polish geophysicists, together with scientists from Italy, have been strongly involved in the creation of large research infrastructures, particularly SIOS (Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System), which received funding under Horizon 2020.

After the organization phase, SIOS went to the implementation phase in 2014, creating partner international consortia, and obtaining funding for this from research and science funding agencies in individual countries. From the very beginning, representatives of Poland and Italy joined the strict bodies managing this platform, largely contributing to achieving the operational phase in 2018-2019. In this context, since then, they have continued to work together in the frame of this initiative to build an integrated monitoring system in the Svalbard Archipelago and make the obtained data available following FAIR principles (findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability).

For the integrity and compatibility of the acquired data, special procedures for the verification of research results have been launched, including pilot projects for selected specialist observations.

The organization of the seminar session at the Polish Scientific Station of the Polish Academy of Sciences in Rome will be an opportunity to summarize the substantive contribution of Polish and Italian scientists to SIOS, which is included as relevant Research Infrastructure both in the Polish Roadmap for Research Infrastructures and Italian Piano Nazionale per le Infrastructure (PNIR 2021-2027) in the area of Earth System science. The meeting will offer the opportunity to discuss how to reinforce cooperation and networking, as well as joint applications to the European Commission in the Horizon Europe programme and bilateral agreements between Poland and Italy.

OVERALL AND SPECIFIC TARGETS

To be concrete, we will focus on areas of environmental sciences where the cooperation in the last years has developed yet thanks to joint activities and actions promoted by SIOS. Namely, these areas are CRYOSPHERE, MARINE SCIENCES, HYDROLOGY/INTERNAL WATERS, and ATMOSPHERE. In addition, how to raise cooperation in the crucial area of high Education for new generations of Arctic/polar researchers will also be discussed/analyzed. Additional themes will be dedicated to effective science communication and all-level education.

Specific aims of the meeting will be:

- Assess the status of cooperation and the strength of its future, in the frame of SIOS and beyond.
- Reinforce cooperation in the crucial area of High Education and science communication
- Stimulate ideas and cooperation devoted to better use of new technologies for long-term observations in polar regions.

Photo: Dariusz Ignatiuk

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AGENDA

Tuesday, December 10

- 12:30 – 13:30 Registration and Lunch
13:30 – 14:00 Welcome and Introductory session
14:00 – 16:00 Assess the status of cooperation:
CRYOSPHERE (4 presentations x 10 min + 20 min discussion)
Italy (Roberto Salzano/Andrea Spolaor)
Poland (Bartek Luks/Dariusz Ignatiuk)
HYDROLOGY/INTERNAL WATERS (4 presentations x 10 min + 20 min discussion)
Italy (Maurizio Azzaro/Marco Doveri)
Poland (Marzena Osuch/ Michael Nones)
16:00 – 16:15 Coffee Break
16:15 – 18:00 Assess the status of cooperation:
ATMOSPHERE (4 presentations x 10 min + 10 min discussion)
Italy (Mauro Mazzola/Stefania Gilardoni)
Poland (Aleksander Pietruczuk/Daniel Kępski)
HIGH EDUCATION and SCIENCE COMMUNICATION (4 presentations x 10 min + 15 min discussion)
Italy (Carlo Barbante/Maria Pia Casarini)
Poland (Agata Goździk/Michał Ciepły/Monika Kalinowska)
19:00 – Workshop Dinner

Wednesday, December 11

- 09:00 – 10:10 Assess the status of cooperation:
MARINE SCIENCES (5 presentations x 10 min + 20 min discussion)
Italy (Manuel Bensi/Gabriella Caruso)
Poland (Agata Zaborska/Agnieszka Strzelewicz/Mateusz Moskalik)
10:10 – 11:00 Improve bilateral cooperation using SIOS
Word about SIOS – Heikki Livahainen/Ilkka Matero
Expanding cooperation to other fields of science
Italy (Roberto Ambrosini/Silvio Marta/Gianmarco Mugnai/Nunziatina Porcino/Karen Garboldi)
Poland (Anna Pieńkowski/Łukasz Grewling/Rafał Szaniawski)
11:00 – 11:15 Coffee Break
11:15 – 12:30 Discussion to identify common priorities and how to better use
Food for discussion (Italy) (Vito Vitale)
Food for discussion (Poland) (Dariusz Ignatiuk)
12:30 – 13:30 Lunch
13:30 – 14:45 More instruments and opportunities to Improve bilateral Cooperation
NCN perspective (Barbara Świątkowska)
PolSCA PAN perspective (TBD)
Discussion to identify common priorities and suitable
Instruments (Piotr Głowacki/Rafał Szaniawski/Michał Ciepły/Caro Barbante/Vito Vitale)
14:45 – 15:00 Coffee Break
15:00 – 16:30 Write UP: how concretely move steps forward

Organizing committee:

Agnieszka Stefaniak-Hrycko
Director of the Scientific Centre Polish Academy of Sciences in Rome
Prof. Piotr Glowacki
Committee for Polar Research Polish Academy of Sciences
Dr. Vito Vitale
National Research Council of Italy, Institute of Polar Sciences

REPORT

Report on the conference organized jointly by the Scientific Station of the Polish Academy of Sciences in Rome and the Institute of Geophysics of the Polish Academy of Sciences on December 10-11, 2024

The Conference, titled: Polish-Italian cooperation in environmental risk assessment using the European research platform SIOS - Exploration and identification of national and EU funding instruments/opportunities and good practices for cooperation with the EU PolarNet and the bilateral HarSval project, was attended by 38 people including 18 people from Italy and 19 people from Poland and a representative of the Knowledge Center SIOS from Svalbard.

The purpose of the meeting was:

- Assessing the state of cooperation and the strength of its future within and beyond SIOS.
- Strengthening cooperation in the key area of higher education and science communication.
- Stimulating ideas and cooperation dedicated to better use of new technologies for long-term observations in the polar regions.

Conference participants were welcomed by Ms. Agnieszka Stefaniak-Hrycko, Director of the Scientific Station in Rome, Prof. Piotr Glowacki and Dr. Vito Vitale, responsible for the content preparation and conduct of the proceedings.

On the first day of the Conference the introduction word on Polish-Italian cooperation was given by Professor Francesco Petracchini - Head of the Earth and Environmental Department of CNR, and the second day of the Conference was opened with a short speech by Professor Marek Konarzewski - President of the Polish Academy of Sciences.

The conference had a seminar and workshop character and was divided into four subject matter-focused panel sessions, during which scientists from Italy and Poland presented in their papers and presentations the current results of their research on Svalbard, and the scope of joint work and plans for the coming years. Each panel ended with discussions, additions and questions about specific research plans.

The first panel on the Cryosphere was led by Dr. Bartłomiej Luks from the Institute of Geophysics of the Polish Academy of Sciences in Warsaw and the panelists were Dr. Roberto Salzano and Dr. Andrea Spolaor and Dariusz Ignatiuk. The basis for the discussion was their joint presentation entitled *Fostering interdisciplinary research cooperation in the cryosphere*.

The second panel dealt with water issues and hydrology not only of the polar regions and was led by Prof. Marzena Osuch of the Institute of Geophysics of the Polish Academy of Sciences, who gave a multi-author presentation entitled *Changes in hydrological processes in the catchments of SW Spitsbergen*. Meanwhile, Dr. Mauricio Azzaro gave a presentation titled *Assessment of the state of cooperation on the study of lakes and reservoirs*. The third presentation, entitled *Remote sensing of inland waters*, was given by Michael Nones. Dr. Marco Doveri was also a panelist in this section.

The third panel was devoted to the problems of atmospheric research and was chaired by Prof. Alexander Pietruczuk with an introduction and presentation entitled *The physics of the atmosphere - who we are*, while Dr. Daniel Kępski gave a presentation entitled *Monitoring the atmosphere at the Hornsund station*, the results of many years of research and monitoring conducted at the Polish Polar Station on Spitsbergen. Italian panelists Dr. Mauro Mazzola and Dr. Stefania Gilardoni presented the scope of research and monitoring carried out at their station in Ny-Alesund on Svalbard.

The session of the first day ended with the panel HIGHER EDUCATION - SCIENCE COMMUNICATION led by Dr. Agata Goździk from IGF PAN and a presentation entitled *How to use the Arctic as a tool to arouse interest in science?* As a panelist, Dr. Maria Pia Casarini gave an online presentation, presenting the possibilities of using polar issues in the programs of the broader education of the public and especially schoolchildren. The other two panelists, Prof. Monika Kalinowska, in her presentation entitled *Doctoral Studies at the Institute of Geophysics of the Polish Academy of Sciences*, referred to the possibilities of specialized training within the framework of doctoral schools. This topic was developed by Dr. Michal Cieplý - Dean of the International Environmental Doctoral School at the Center for Polar Studies at the University of Silesia. The first day of the conference ended with a formal dinner and roundtable discussions.

Photo: Dariusz Ignatiuk

The second day of the conference, following the PAS President's address, began with a panel on Oceanographic Research in Svalbard and the North Atlantic. This panel was chaired by Dr. Manuel Bensi and presented a paper titled *“Italian marine infrastructure on Svalbard: an opportunity for cooperation,”* and Dr. Gabriella Caruso presented research opportunities titled *“Coastal thalassographic buoy - Ny-Alesund.* Polish panelists Prof. Mateusz Moskalik

presented *“Oceanographic monitoring in Hornsund fjord, Spitsbergen”*. Prof. Agata Zaborska presented the results of the study *“Quantification of heavy metal emissions with freshwater runoff into the Arctic fjord ecosystem (Hornsund, Spitsbergen) Quantification of heavy metal emissions with freshwater runoff into the Arctic fjord ecosystem (Hornsund, Spitsbergen),”* and Dr. Agnieszka Strzelewicz presented the results of the multi-year ARES oceanographic program in the Svalbard area.

In the pre-lunch session, Ilkka Matero from the SIOS Knowledge Centre in Longyearbyen presented the main undertakings of the international Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System Consortium and expectations and international cooperation primarily in sharing FAIR data from Polish and Italian monitoring in the Svalbard area.

One of the most important sessions of this conference was the session devoted to expanding Polish-Italian cooperation into new fields and research topics. In this session, seven representatives from Italian scientific and university institutions and 3 people from Poland made their presentations. The session was chaired by Prof. Rafal Szaniawski - Deputy Director for Scientific Affairs of the Institute of Geophysics of the Polish Academy of Sciences, who in his presentation touched on the geological research of paleomagnetism and seismology on Svalbard. Dr. Roberto Ambrosini presented a glacio-ecological research program, while Dr. Mariasilvia Giamberini presented *“The Changing Critical Zone of the Tundra on Svalbard”*; Dr. Gianmarco Mugnai *“Exploring the Limits of Microorganisms in Arctic Environments: Opportunities and Challenges”*; Dr. Francesca Pittino *“Microbial Ecology - Microbial Ecology of Glacial Environments”*; Dr. Karen Gariboldi presented issues of micropaleontological research; PhD Nunziatina Poreino issues of heavy metal pollution of waters; Dr. Silvo Marta *“Proglacial environments: patterns, processes, protection and services”*. In addition, Polish proposals for developing cooperation were presented by Prof. Anna Pienkowski and Prof. Lukasz Grewling on aerobiology and paleostratigraphy of sediments and cores.

In the session after lunch, the possibilities of expanding cooperation with the use of European funds and bilateral agreements were presented by the representative of the National Science Center - Barbara Swiatkowska and the National Contact Point Deputy Director Maria Smietanko.

The remaining time until the end of the conference was devoted to a discussion of the possibilities and means of expanding Polish-Italian cooperation with new partners and new research directions especially in preparation for the 5th International Polar Year. This session was jointly chaired by Dr. Vito Vitale on behalf of the CNR and Dr. Dariusz Ignatiuk on behalf of the Polish Polar Consortium, delivering their proposals and thoughts. Particular attention was paid to developing cooperation in doctoral school education through the departure of doctoral students for internships at Polish and Italian scientific institutions, the arrival of specialists for specialized lectures, or the joint conduct of doctoral projects through dual promotorship and the simultaneous conferral of doctoral degrees in Poland and Italy.

At the end of the conference, Prof. Piotr Głowacki thanked all participants for their prepared speeches and very fruitful discussion and suggestions for further activities. He paid special tribute to the staff of the Scientific Station of the Polish Academy of Sciences in Rome for their preparation and assistance in organizing the entire event.

In general, it can be emphasized that the organization of the seminar session at the Polish Scientific Station of the Polish Academy of Sciences in Rome was an opportunity to summarize the substantive contribution of Polish and Italian scientists to SIOS, which is included as an important Research Infrastructure in both the Polish Roadmap for Research

Infrastructures and the Italian Piano Nazionale per le Infrastructure (PNIR 2021-2027) in the area of Earth System Sciences. The meeting was an opportunity to discuss ways to strengthen cooperation and networking, as well as joint applications to the European Commission in Horizon Europe and bilateral agreements between Poland and Italy.

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President of the Organizing Committee
Prof. Dr. Piotr Głowacki

Photo: <https://rzym.pan.pl/en/blog/2024/12/03/polish-italian-cooperation-in-assessing-environmental-threats-10-11-12-2024/>